

Selected Shakespearean Tragic Plays: Error of Judgment of the Characters and Its Implication to Teaching Literature

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Abstract

This study focused on the error of judgment of the characters in selected Shakespeare's major plays: Hamlet, Romeo and Juliet, King Lear, Othello, Antony and Cleopatra. It analyzed the tragic flaw found in the events, theme, setting, and characterization. The error of judgment of the characters as the cause of their downfall are identified by the use of the literary device Hamartia as outlined by Aristotle in his Poetics. This presented its implications in teaching literature. This is a qualitative descriptive- analytical anchored by textual analysis. It utilized analytical description in the concept of errors found in Shakespeare's tragic plays. The plays of Shakespeare are indisputably the greatest tragedian in the field of writing because of his overreaching protagonists which also are tragic heroes. It stipulates some flaws which led to their destruction. It was determined that the protagonists in the plays show some flaws in the events, how the plays change from happiness to misery because of errors; setting, the time and place in which the action of the tragedy occurred; theme, which represents the kind of tragedy and lastly the characterization, by pointing out the qualities and their deeds.

Keywords: Shakespearean play. Tragedy. Flaws. Literature. Error.

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Introduction

Literature is an art. It has a creative value on different levels including the traits of every individual, either positive or negative which can result to a flaw or an error. Discussing tragedy is a tricky business. It deals with issues that are significant and far-reaching. That is why most of the theme of tragedies deal with someone's death. Stating tragedy would not be tragedy if it were not manifest misery.

Moreover, tragedy cannot be conceived without enumerating the characters who are the main subject of the issue. The one who experiences all kinds of occurrence and control conspicuous events in some way. The act which is applicable to their personalities, the credibility or otherwise to the situations and other stations of life. The tragic characters then will be defined according to good and horrible deeds. As a result, an error occurs where a character either does it consciously or does it out of ignorance or mediates it.

The researchers examined some of the major tragic plays written by William Shakespeare. These major plays are the Hamlet, Romeo and Juliet, King Lear, Othello, Antony, and Cleopatra. In particular, this work of art deals briefly with the error of judgment which inevitably led to the tragic downfall of the characters particularly the protagonist in each play. The researchers examined first the tragic flaw found in the plays of Shakespeare in accordance with events, setting, theme, and characterization. Hence, this can lead to the main aim of the study of finding out errors of judgement among the characters in the plays involved.

In addition, since the tragic plays of Shakespeare are also part of literature, emphasis is on the implications of the study's findings to teaching literature. This will reflect on additional learning, where every tragic story as being encountered by the people. The traits of the characters that influence the actions either positive or negative may cause errors which may lead to tragic downfall. Even honour does not have the strength to overcome reason in order to guide men's action towards tragic ends. Even their expertise in not being wounded by experiences, often result in death. Every individual has to face barriers with very serious decision; and rationality makes the individual learn from mistakes.

This study can widen the perspectives of the future educators in analysing the plays of William Shakespeare. By letting them figure out and define the means of tragic flaw as reflected in the tragic character which result to their downfall; and make them more sensitive and extra-careful by focusing on one point too intensely to such genre as tragedy. As literature enthusiasts and education practitioners, it will also be a great contribution to their body of knowledge. By letting them show awareness in literary context within the notions of tragedy; to be familiar on the tragic plays of Shakespeare since it is also part of literature, especially the sequence of events where the tragedy occurs, emphasizing how the plays becomes tragic, and more importantly the main characters who experience this occurrence.

Furthermore, the plays are in its consequential genre, hence, it opens the readers interest and seriousness of rifling through the other plays of tragedies by Shakespeare. To substantiate the literariness of the medium used, the researchers decided to make use of the book, together with the complete scenes of the play via online searching since the resources that can be found in the library are also limited. Much of the references had be taken from the internet as well. The lines being spoken by the characters and the complete segments of the play were imperative.

Review of Related Literature

Tragedy is often used loosely to describe any sort of disaster or misfortune. Katawazai (2018) explored his studies in artistic values of the play *Romeo and Juliet* by William Shakespeare. The love and hate both go similarly in the play. It gives the emotional feelings of sadness and happiness to the readers. Moreover, Kodal (2019) noted that Cleopatra's role in the play leads gradual downfall of Anthony. Cleopatra's character is worth being analyzed whether she plays a submissive or a subversive role in the collapse of Antony, while in Karnewar (2019) presented different misdeeds of King Lear as a king and as a parent at the same time the ungrateful attitude of him. Furthermore, Gottlieb (2009) studied the critical shift from finding a flaw in a tragedy's hero to understanding tragedy as a genre that by definition has a flawed hero, with the audience and the performance experience falling by the wayside. The former focuses on a play's experience: the confrontation with the Open takes on a more dreadful tone through the exposure of the flaw in greatness.

Gottlieb (2009) added that most academicians "solve" the paradox with which tragedy presents us by either disregarding it completely of a more abstract reading based on the text's material existence and its cultural particularities, or by merely dissolving the paradox—justifying the hero's suffering by pointing to its utility in terms of the audience's moral instruction or by attributing the suffering to the hero's "tragic flaw" or an intellectual error. However, in both dissolving and disregarding the tragic tension, we frequently choose our cerebral, post hoc interpretations of the drama over our more immediate, less cerebral reactions, which are as genuine.

Mueller (2009), in the book *The Iliad*, said that the Homeric warriors have a pitifully developed sense of dependability. Dependability to a common cause runs a destitute third to the journey for person honor and the commitment to a quick brother or companion in arms. Indeed, in this pecking order of values Achilles' ask sums to conspiracy, and, as events will show, it may be a hamartia in Aristotle's sense, a deplorable blunder of judgment the mortal results of which can bounce back upon Achilles himself. Moreover, it is stated in the book that Achilles lives his life as a grand warrior, believing that he is invulnerable. Thus, Achilles' tragic flaw was his pride, which forced him to flee the battle. Patroclus, one of the few human beings Achilles seemed to care about, died as a result of this.

According to Charlton (1948), in the end, the audience wins "spiritually" from the hero's downfall, and therefore tragedy serves as a function of our species' moral growth. Even if, critically, the audience in the theater does not instantly realize the reality, the hero's suffering—and our delighted terror as we watch it unfold—makes sense in light of humanity's progress.

In presenting hamartia as the protagonist's "tragic fault" (Hyde, 1963), numerous Aristotelian translators have set off what Rosenstein (1977) dubbed the "hamartia hunt," a way of interpreting the tragic hero from a merely pathological viewpoint. This method is based on the notion that negative consequences must have rationally discernible and equally unfavorable causes, and it aims to discover the protagonist's dysfunctional aspect.

Linn (2001) stated that some characters in *The Iliad*, such as Agamemnon, demonstrated hamartia by walking over tapestries depicting gods' representations. Many considered his pursuit of honors to be extravagant. Despite the fact that Agamemnon professes himself to be a man and not a deity, he requests that mankind adore him. Agamemnon proclaims himself to be more powerful than the gods in general. His open contempt for the power of the gods, as well as his demand to be held up as a deity, revealed that he had fatality flaws, or hamartia.

Moreover, the undisputed commander of the Trojan army Hector works as an agent to bring Achilles back into combat after Hector assassinates Patroclus, and Achilles feels he has no option but to repay Patroclus by killing Hector. As a result, Hector will almost certainly fall victim to Achilles. However, it is important to note that Hector is enslaved by the illusion of a Trojan victory, a victory that appears to have been assured by Zeus himself. Hector's never-ending battle, which everyone, including himself, knows he was condemned by fate since he was under the illusion of a Trojan victory.

The book *Oedipus Rex*, which was translated by David Mulroy in 2011, stated that of the characters in the Sophocles' *Oedipus the King*, also filled with the errors of judgment as the cause of their downfall. Oedipus hamartia was stated because of his determination. It is proven that Oedipus would never have learnt the tragic reality of his existence if he had not been so anxious to know the identity of Laius' real killer. Oedipus is likewise engulfed with rage. Indeed, it was impulsive anger that drove him to slay his true father, King Laius, at the crossroads. The killing of Oedipus' father is a crucial connection in his demise. Jocasta, mother of Oedipus also integrated a sort of hamartia; it is also found in the book that, Jocasta's hamartia, or downfall, is linked to her experimentation with authority.

Meanwhile, Carey et al. (2015), also shows an error of judgment of the main character in the Christopher Marlowe's *Dr. Faustus*. She stated that Faustus certainly enjoys great reputations and prosperity. His misfortune was not brought upon him by depravity, but by "hubris" which could be called his tragic flaw especially since, when his pride left him in the second act, it has been replaced with despair and this is the flip-side of pride. He judges his own sins instead of humbly asking for God's forgiveness. However, it could be argued that he gambles hell as a fable, and this gamble turns out to be an error of judgement.

Bloom (2010) also suggested that in the book *The Great Gatsby* it was discussed how the protagonist committed tragic downfall. It included some qualities and the deeds of the main character, that Gatsby attempts to believe in the vision of himself that he has built. He became rich through doubtful means but manages to progress a clean "preppy" look. He maintains his status by having lavish parties but does not seem to really care too much about the friends he invites. He remains disconnected from the people. He is a loner in the crowd. Gatsby was relatively unselfish in his life, and whose primary flaw was his naïve idealism.

Radzinowicz (2015) cited about Samson, a bible character whose error of judgment was related to a woman, Delilah. His passion for her, an evil woman hired by the Philistine to discover the source of his immense strength. Delilah's servant shaves his hair and takes away his strength when he eventually admits his strength is due to his long hair. In addition, Sowerby (2014), stated that Medea's hamartia is her love to Jason that is so passionate. When Jason cheated on her, she is willing to do anything her revenge. Medea is so overcome with hatred and rage that she kills Jason's new bride, the King, and both of her own children. As Medea says, "I have done it: because I loathed you more than I loved them. Mine is the triumph," she realizes that what she is doing is wrong, but her appalling imperfection overcomes her, so she must act upon it.

Finally, Bloom (2009) also stated the error of judgment in the literary work of Mary Shelley about Frankenstein who believes he can become scientist unparalleled in ability to do science stuff. He starts to create life. He thinks that he can create a monster that is at par with man. But this monster then goes around killing everything Victor loves. Victor's ability for science took him down. His desire on the creation of his own design led to his destruction.

Methodology

Theoretical Framework

This is a qualitative research study, particularly, descriptive- analytical using textual analysis focused on the errors of judgment of the protagonists in Shakespeare's tragic plays. It utilized analytical description in the concept of errors found in Shakespeare's tragic plays.

This is anchored on the literary device Hamartia, first described in the subject of literary criticism by Aristotle in his Poetics, which also guides this study. The rise of hamartia is at the juncture between character and the character's actions, or behaviors as outlined by Aristotle: "Character in a play is that which reveals the moral purpose of the agents, i.e. the sort of thing they seek or avoid."

In tragedy, the literary device hamartia is usually understood to relate to the protagonist's error, which causes a sequence of narrative events to culminate in a reversal of their good fortune to bad fate. What qualifies as imperfection can include an error resulting from ignorance, an error of judgment, or a flaw in character.

In addition, this study also employed the formalistic approach to literary criticism to help them identify the effective values (mood, atmosphere, attitude), ideational values (theme, universal truth, character) and technical values (plot, imagery, figure of speech) of the text to which the needed findings significantly have associations.

Conceptual Framework

This study is anchored on different literary and communicative theories, thus directing this work of art into becoming an academic masterpiece. The notion about tragedy focusing on the errors of judgment is best taught through the realistic pictures of which literature provides. People, for some kind of matter takes a hard time not to commit errors throughout their lives. These errors are used as examples of the general problem which signify the traits or actions of the individual, leading to tragic downfall. Tragedy frequently springs from the individual conflict with values.

As these tragic plays selected by the researchers are believed to be of the contemporary genre in the written works of Shakespeare, the researchers examined first the tragic flaw found in each play, how the selected tragic plays have flawed in accordance to the: a.) Event, how the play changes from bliss to misery because of mistakes; b.) Setting, the time and place in which the action of the tragedy occur; c.) Themes, which represents the kind of tragedy; and d.) Characterization, by pointing out the qualities and their deeds in the play.

Moreover, since the researchers found out that the Shakespearean plays contain tragic death, they have come up that the tragic characters specifically the protagonist in each play has its error of judgement as the cause of their tragic downfall. The researchers used this as the main aim of the study, i.e., to find out the errors of judgment of the characters in each play of Shakespeare.

Finding out the tragic flaw in terms of the events, setting, themes and characterization are extracted and articulated using textual analysis. This also serves as a framework for the findings. In addition, the researchers also give emphasis to the implications of this study to literature teaching.

Research Procedure

The researchers read the tragic plays so as to have a general idea and understand the sequence of the events in the play. Since this is the interest of the researchers to conduct study in the tragic plays of Shakespeare, a systematic extraction of the needed data for the study to find answers to the stated objectives was undertaken. This study followed a definite procedure to come up with a reliable, precise, and accurate analysis of the medium used. The hereunder statements systematically developed the flow of the study.

- a.) The researchers examined the tragic flaws reflected in the tragic plays of Shakespeare in accordance with the event, setting, theme, and characterization through textual analysis.
- b.) The researchers were to find out the cause of the tragic downfall of the characters involved in each play, which is the main aim of the study on the errors of judgment of the characters, particularly the protagonists.
- c.) Moreover, the researchers were to come up with implication from the findings of this study to literature teaching.

Framework Analysis

The researchers incorporated ideas from literary device called hamartia by Aristotle, and the formalistic approach. The main objective of this study is to give emphasis to the error of judgment of the characters found in five (5) major plays of Shakespeare and show that this error has to do with their downfall. The researchers included characters: only the protagonists who died in the play and have huge parts in the tragic plays, and in turn, provided significance how the plays of Shakespeare become tragic. The source of hamartia is at a point between character and character's actions or behaviours. In this sense, it is commonly understood that the character's flaw that leads to a chain of plot actions peak in a reversal from their good to bad fortune. These connections were traced and attributes that were carried in the plays of Shakespeare were explicated as to how they give emphasis to form a tragic genre.

With all of these analyses, the flaws or error of the characters which led to their downfall were presented. Aristotle's hamartia is a literary device which links to the functioning of a tragedy. The researchers presented this literary device for use in the findings of the study, to help them come up with generalizations on the tragic downfall of the protagonists in the plays, thus the error of the characters is drawn.

Analysis and Interpretation of Data

Tragic flaws reflected in each of the Shakespearean tragedy

Romeo and Juliet

Event

This play demonstrates that though love has its considerable strength, fate, still, caused a substantial conflict to the couple. Whereas Romeo was involved in an unreciprocated love with Rosaline, Juliet lived a carefree life. Juliet was always introduced by her mother to varied marriage opportunities, but things changed when she met Romeo. At the party, Romeo's only intention was to meet Rosaline not until the moment he laid his eyes on Juliet, after which, Rosaline stopped existing in his life. With destiny and love at first sight, the struggle of this partner began which led to an appalling conclusion.

Theme

This piece centers on romantic love, especially on the intensity of desire that started on the first meeting of the couple. Love was set in a pedestal in a way that it is impressive but at the same time blinding, just as the concept of hatred can. Here, love was able to also cause violence and these two ideas also intertwined in exact moments. The strong desire that sprung between Romeo and Juliet almost also started at the time that Tybalt—who intends to kill Romeo, found him at the party. It looked as if love thrust the two towards love and viciousness, instead of bringing them away from it.

Setting

In the play, it shows that Romeo is acknowledging the fact that he is going to die in his own hand. He is doing so for his wife, Juliet. As part of the play, it can be inferred that the feud is between the two powerful families in Verona, the Montague and the Capulet. The reason for the feud is both old and bitter. Capulets don't like the Montagues because of their identity, and that feeling is mutual. While neither side really elaborates upon why the hatred is still present, that Romeo and Juliet continue to engage each other in acts of aggression and conflict.

Characterization

**“Is she a Capulet?
O dear account! My life is my foe's debt.”**

-Romeo (Act I, scene 5)

Romeo was not able or unaware that the woman he loves is a Capulet. He fought for love; he would rather die with love without his beloved. He was obligated to be with the Juliet, who was a rival in the eyes of his father. He knew the risk that they took.

**“My only love sprung from my only fate
Too early seen unknown, and known too late!
Prodigious birth of love it is me.
That I must love a loathed.”**

-Juliet (Act I, scene 5)

It was not immediate for Juliet to comprehend that the boy she loved is unfortunately, the son of his father's enemy. The Capulets and Montagues have had a long-time conflict with each other. The moment she knew, she then recognized the seriousness of what she got herself into. Nevertheless, the two believed that their love will fix everything. Unfortunately, the supreme thing that they have is also that which led to their demise. Fate played against them.

Both of them were incapable and disinclined to think about the results of their actions. The deed of Romeo is deliberately done when he committed suicide by taking poison, not realizing Juliet was pretending as dead in order for her to be with Romeo. Unfortunately, this false act led to their tragic end.

Likewise, Frankenstein who believes he can become scientist unparalleled in ability to do science stuff. Frankenstein starts to create life. He thinks that he can create a monster that is at par with man. He never also considered if what would be the consequences of creating a monster. His desire on the creation of his own design is his own error of judgment, also the same with the desire of Romeo to be with the side of Juliet.

King Lear

Event

The play is about the king and his three daughters, while the two sisters plot to seize power. Lear is an aged, well-off man who, naturally betroths his wealth to his daughters. However, this promise did not go well and eventually caused his devastation. It was too late for him to realize that his two old daughters were plotting against him. This action led to his fall out from his regal highness and family misfortune.

Theme

The typical conflict—good versus evil—is utilized in this play. The king puts his daughter's into trial and values the extravagant pronouncements of love from Regan and Goneril. This doubtful display of love bothered him more than the profound silence of Cordelia. She persisted to be loyal to his father. She declines to revolt against Lear even after she was maltreated by him. On the other hand, her sisters continued their deception which ultimately proves to be a success.

Setting

The made-up ruler of England, King Lear has always made choices that incredibly changed his and the lives of people that surround him. His decision to fight for his authority is the root cause of all his misery, to the point that it took the lives of those who took part in these events.

Characterization

**“O, reason not the need! Our basest beggars
 Are in the poorest thing superfluous.
 Allow not nature more than nature needs,
 Man’s life’s as cheap as beast’s...”**

...

You heavens, give me that patience, patience I need!

...

**If it be you that stir these daughters’ hearts
 Against their father, fool me not so much
 To bare it timely; touch me with noble anger,
 And let not women’s weapons, water-drops,
 Stain my man’s cheeks! No, you unnatural hags,**

...

No, I’ll not weep.

**I have full cause of weeping, but this heart
 Shall break into a hundred thousand flaws,
 Or ere I’ll weep. O fool, I shall go mad!”**

-King Lear (Act II, scene 4)

Lear conveys the above lines after his patience was exhausted by the savageries of Goneril and Regan. He seethes against the two, exclaiming that their efforts to strip him off of his subordinates greatly affected him. “O, reason not the need!” he cries saying that there would be no distinction between humans and animals if happiness is not essential for humans to live. Lear’s need for his followers is not only of their service but also of what they symbolize—his identity as a powerful king and a human. When Goneril and Regan took this from Lear, the latter’s identity was also reduced. They drove him mad, as depicted in the final lines of the quote above, particularly because he could not accept his daughter’s disloyalty. Here, he realizes that he is weak, and he can only rant as an outlet for his anger.

**Lear: What! Has his daughters brought him to this pass?
 Couldst thou save nothing? Wouldst’t thou give ‘em all?
 Fool: Nay, he reserv’d a blanket, else we had been all sham’d.
 Lear: Now all the plagues that in the pendulous air
 Hand fated o’er mens faults light on thy daughters!**

-King Lear (Act III, scene 4)

Lear’s realization of his poor actions made way to his reconnection with Cordelia, the love of his life. However, their reunion also led to their death. This could have been prevented by other characters, but fate was overpowering. In the end, Lear held her daughter as she was dying.

His downfall was primarily caused by his hasty decision as to whom he would pass his kingdom, based on their pronouncements of love. He thought that if he managed his wealth in this manner, rivalry will be avoided—but he was wrong. This act of Lear is what caused him all of the turmoil he encountered. Moreover, this is also related in the story of Dr. Faustus who deliberately offered his life and soul to the demon for the sake of fame and power but unfortunately turns out to regrets and sufferings.

Hamlet

Event

Hamlet visits his mother to confront her. When he goes to her room, Polonius concealed himself behind an artistic piece of drapery. However, Hamlet notices this, draws his sword and pierced the drapestry, ultimately slaying Polonius. Because of this, he was immediately exiled to Britain with Rosencrantz and Guildenstern. Secretly, Claudius has planned for his death instead of just his exile.

Ophelia was maddened with sorrow following her father’s death and drowns herself in the river. Polonius’s son, Laertes, went back to Denmark with anguish. He was influenced by Claudius that Hamlet was at fault for the death of his father and sisters, thus Laertes was enraged. Claudius used his anger to plan for Hamlet’s death. In a fencing sport, Laertes will match against Hamlet, but Claudius planned to poison Laertes sword so that it would be fatal to his opponent. To further empty his plot of all mistakes, he also poisoned a goblet that Hamlet will use if he scores in the first and second hits of the contest. During Ophelia’s funeral, Hamlet returns to Elsinore. He attacked Laertes and exclaimed his love for Ophelia. Meanwhile at the castle, Hamlet also says to Horatio that a person must always be prepared for death because it may come at any time.

Theme

Hamlet shows that our actions are affected not only by rationality but also of our emotions, ethics and psyche. He seems to believe that it is impossible for one to have full control of his/her actions. Thus, when he acts, he favors to do it an uncritical and vicious manner. Other characters also give less consideration on “action” compared to Hamlet. They worry less on the efficacy of their movements and act according to what suits them. Nevertheless, Hamlet proves to be correct because their acts tend to fail. Claudius was able to get hold of the crown, but his sense of morality eventually tortures him. Furthermore, he was plagued with pressures to his power. On the other hand, Laertes is steadfast with his goal of revenge, but it turned out that he was simply wrought into helping Claudius’s will and his plots of poisoning backfired.

Setting

Hamlet binds himself to violence when he struck Polonius through the drapery and also takes himself to an inevitable problem with the king. This is in Act 2 Scene 4. The end of Act 4, Scene 4 is a potential climax when Hamlet committed his brutal vengeance.

Moreover, he believes to be responsible in taking vengeance for his father’s death, against Claudius. The latter however becomes king thus making it difficult for Hamlet to do so. He qualms if it right to trust the apparition that pushed him to kill Claudius.

The ghost showed itself to Hamlet telling him to avenge its murder where he responds a pretentious insanity to this idea. Hamlet passes up the opportunity to kill Claudius while he is praying. Hamlet is exiled to England to be murdered. He returned to Denmark and settled his conflict with Laertes during the burial of Ophelia and fence contest.

Characterization

**“To be, or not to be—that is the question:
Whether ’tis nobler for the mind to suffer
The slings and arrows of outrageous fortune
Or to take arms against a sea of troubles
And by opposing end them. To die, to sleep...”**

-Hamlet (Act III, scene 1)

Hamlet planned to kill the person who he thought killed his father—Claudius. He wanted to first, find evidence before he does his action and in turn it destroys his life. As he tries to settle this conflict in his life, his relationship with his mother is stained and causes Ophelia to commit suicide because of depression. His hesitation to do vengeance caused death of many.

**“O, what a rogue and peasant slave am I!
Is it not monstrous that this player here,
But in a fiction, in a dream of passion,
Could force his soul so to his own conceit
That from her working all his visage waned,
Tears in his eyes, distraction in his aspect,
A broken voice, and his whole function suiting
With forms to his conceit—and all for nothing!”**

-Hamlet (Act III, Scene 4)

Hamlet rebukes himself because he was not able to get justice for his father’s death. Just like any other son, he wants to take revenge for the death of his father, but he was unable to do it because there is a hindrance in doing it. He was very disgusted by the marriage of his newly widowed mother, Queen Gertrude to his uncle, King Hamlet’s brother, Claudius, who has the throne already. He does not want Claudius to rule the kingdom where once his father did. And because of too much anger at Claudius, Hamlet put himself to death.

**“When honor’s at the stake. How stand I, then,
That have a father killed, a mother stained,
Excitements of my reason and my blood,
And let all sleep, while, to my shame, I see
The imminent death of twenty thousand men
That, for a fantasy and trick of fame
Go to their graves like beds, fight for a plot
Whereon the numbers cannot try the cause,
Which is not tomb enough and continent
To hide the slain? O, from this time forth
My thoughts be bloody, or be nothing worth!”**

-Hamlet (Act IV, scene 4)

This is a defining moment for Hamlet. Watching the army of Fortinbras approach his fortress, he envisions that many lives would be lost fighting an irrelevant cause. He felt embarrassed that he was not able to seek retributions for his father’s death and mother’s dignity. Here, Hamlet’s views gone to full violence as he selects the path of his actions.

Hamlet is deliberate to kill Claudius. With this, he was also killed. His indecisiveness in doing this act led to his downfall. There the hamartia takes place, where Hamlet kills Claudius and did not think of the consequences he would go through. Similar to what Oedipus did to his father where he was also enveloped with temper, and it was only out of a fit of rage that he killed his father at the crossroads. This act led to his downfall.

Othello

Event

Othello is portrayed as a diffident man of color, married to a woman who is White. He lives in Venice. Though he is exceedingly respected in the military, he still carries a lot of insecurity. Iago is his trusted friend, thus when Othello helps Cassio to be a lieutenant, Iago gets envious. This made Iago antagonize Othello, who becomes mistrustful of Desdemona. Othello, being confident of Iago, discloses to him of his plot to kill his wife through poison. But when he learns of Iago’s treachery, he injures Iago and commits suicide.

Theme

Jealousy is represented in varied forms in this play. It pushes Iago to turn his back against his general and destroy him. Othello became skeptic of Desdemona while Roderigo also had the yearning to take Desdemona for himself. The characters were encouraged to act the way they did because of jealousy.

Falsity also played a big part in this play. Iago’s dishonesty and Roderigo’s disposition to antagonize Othello, built an ambiance of doubt and deception. Faith also led to the characters’ downfall, such as Othello’s trust in Iago.

Setting

The two main settings present diverse viewpoints of time and characterization especially of Othello. The story unravels in Venice, the center of civilization for business, defense and chivalry. In this society, Othello is well esteemed. He is recognized in adventures and charms people who surround him especially his wife.

Moving to Cyprus, Othello was supposed to take part in the military expedition against Turks. If this campaign were to transpire, Othello would have been busy with war tactics. Unfortunately, the Turks were crushed, so there was no battle anymore for him to get involved with, giving him more time to think about Iago. He was too engaged to finding an adversary, and this time, he finds Desdemona.

**“Were I the Moor I would not be Iago.
In following him I follow but myself;
Heaven is my judge, not I for love and duty,
But seeming so for my peculiar end.
For when my outward action doth demonstrate
The native act and figure of my heart
In compliment extern, ’tis not long after
But I will wear my heart upon my sleeve
For daws to peck at. I am not what I am.”**

-Iago (Act I, scene 1)

Iago explicates his strategies to Roderigo. He plotted this stratagem because of his suspicion that Othello is having an affair with his wife. He explains that he supports Othello because he could sense that he can easily fool him.

**“Cassio’s a proper man. Let me see now:
 To get his place and to plume up my will
 In double knavery—How, how? Let’s see.
 After some time, to abuse Othello’s ear
 That he is too familiar with his wife.
 He hath a person and a smooth dispose
 To be suspected, framed to make women false.
 The Moor is of a free and open nature,
 That thinks men honest that but seem to be so,
 And will as tenderly be led by th’ nose
 As asses are.
 I have’t. It is engendered. Hell and night
 Must bring this monstrous birth to the world’s light.”**

-Iago (Act I, Scene 3)

Iago asserts that Othello has an affair with his wife, Emilia. Here, Iago shares to the audience his plot to abolish Othello by taking advantage of his foolishness. He will make Othello believe that the latter’s wife is engaged in an extra-marital relationship with Cassio. Iago was determined to use jealousy as a driving force for Othello’s demise. More interestingly, Iago perceives his wicked plan as a “monstrous birth,” that he will get to “light.”

Othello’s acts in the play destroyed himself, by believing Iago’s scheme that his wife Desdemona has a love affair with Rodrigo. Othello’s love for Desdemona caused him to lose control of himself. He is blinded by this love and does not see when he is being conned by Iago. Also, the same with Medea, the tragic character who was passionately in love with Jason. When Jason cheated on her, Medea was blinded with hate and anger, and her jealousy causes her to kill his husband and her children.

Antony and Cleopatra

Event

Antony was a Roman commander and one of the three triumvirs who controlled Rome after Julius Caesar’s death in 44 BC. He falls passionately in love with Cleopatra, Queen of Egypt, renouncing the strict self-control and constraint required of Roman emperors in exchange of the relaxed, laissez-faire morality and lifestyle of the Egyptians. He eventually ignites the wrath of Octavius Caesar, one of his co-rulers. The two men grow to dislike each other and go to war.

In collision with Mark Antony, Cleopatra failed to secure a state independent of the Roman Empire. Realizing she would not be treated well by Octavian for her effort, she committed suicide, marking the end of both the Hellenistic period and of the Ptolemaic dynasty in Egypt. It seems that she must have been a tragic heroine for those who hated the Roman Empire and opposed Roman rule.

Theme

Betrayal imparts the entire part of the play. At the end of the play, Antony chooses to commit suicide since he has compromised his own honor. Despite everything else that has transpired, he regrets the most his failure to be his most noble self. The realization that he has failed to live up to his own principles is the final blow.

The image of Cleopatra’s fleeing ships, on the other hand, appears twice throughout the play. Antony goes to sea twice to fight Caesar, and both times his navy is betrayed by the queen’s retreat. The ships allude to Cleopatra’s inconstancy, as well as the inconstancy of human character in the play. Cleopatra’s allegiance is unclear whether she runs out of fear or because she recognizes that aligning herself with Caesar would be strategically advantageous. Her fleeing ships are an effective symbol of her wavering and changeability.

Setting

The climax happens when Antony loses to Caesar at Actium and destroys all self-respect as a result. From this point on, he gives way to his infatuation, behaving erratically for the quixotic queen, who toy with Antony’s emotions. Antony’s ultimate defeat by Caesar and his separation from Cleopatra are at the focus of the descending action. Antony falls on his own sword and subsequently dies in front of Cleopatra, bringing the story to a conclusion. She completes the tragedy by following him into death with a suicide.

When Cleopatra learns about Antony’s marriage in Egypt, she becomes enraged. When a messenger informs Cleopatra, that Octavia is bland and unattractive, she becomes certain that she will reclaim Antony. Without fighting, the triumvirs meet Pompey and resolve their disagreements. In exchange for authority of Sicily and Sardinia, Pompey offers to safeguard the peace. The four guys drink that evening to commemorate their ceasefire. One of Pompey’s soldiers tells him about a plot to kill the triumvirs and seize world power for himself, but Pompey dismisses the plot as an insult to his dignity. In the meantime, one of Antony’s generals defeats the kingdom of Parthia.

Characterization

**“Let Rome in Tiber melt and the wide arch
 Of the ranged empire fall. Here is my space.
 Kingdoms are clay; our dungy earth alike
 Feeds beast as man. The nobleness of life
 Is to do thus; when such a mutual pair
 And such a twain can do’t, in which I bind,
 On pain of punishment, the world to weet
 We stand up peerless.”**

-Antony (Act I, scene 1)

Antony has not forsaken his concern about power by taking up with Cleopatra—far from it, in fact. Instead, he found the center of his power is with her and their relationship is a symbol of life’s nobleness. This might be taken as a shift in his perspective on power—Rome’s kingdom is itself not built on the clay soil, but the power of love between two people.

**“All is lost;
 This foul Egyptian hath betrayed me:
 My fleet hath yielded to the foe; and yonder
 They cast their caps up and carouse together
 Like friends long lost. Triple-turn’d whore! ‘tis thou
 Hast sold me to this novice; and my heart
 Makes only wars on thee. Bid them all fly;
 For when I am revenged upon my charm,
 I have done all. Bid them all fly; begone.”**

-Antony (Act IV, scene 12)

Antony's statement expresses grief and anger, but he acts in direct opposition to his feelings and words, all for Cleopatra's sake. Antony's pain is oddly subdued for someone who has earned and lost so much. The ironic gap between the character's words and actions creates an ambivalent subject.

Antony was deceived by his own honor in the play. Despite everything else that has occurred, he regrets the most his failure to be his noble self. His error comes when he realizes he has not yet lived up to his own aspirations.

**“Most kind messenger,
Say to great Caesar this in deputation:
I kiss his conqu’ring hand. Tell him I am prompt
To lay my crown at’s feet, and there to kneel.”**

-Cleopatra (Act III, scene 13)

Cleopatra's betrayal was based on her successful fencing with Octavius, which earned her to be “noble to herself”. However, she quickly reconciles with Antony, reaffirming her loyalty towards him and never truly submitting to Caesar.

**“My desolation does begin to make
A better life.
‘Tis paltry to be Caesar:
Not being Fortune, he’s but Fortune’s knave,
A minister of her will.”**

-Cleopatra (Act V, scene 2)

Cleopatra consoles herself after defeat with the thought that it is not Caesar but Fortune that is the victor. This line again illustrates the theme of Fortune and how man is at its whim.

The error of judgment of Cleopatra is deliberate because she chose to betray Antony. With the theme of betrayal, demonstrating how those in positions of authority, no matter how honest their words appear to be, cannot be trusted. The characters' devotion and the truthfulness of their promises are continuously questioned. The constant shifting of alliances adds to the ambiguity and doubt about the character's devotion and betrayal.

Moreover, there is a similarity in the story of Samson and Delilah, where the protagonist of the story was betrayed by a wicked woman named Delilah, who was paid by the Philistine to find the source of his great strength, and also the reason of Samson's downfall.

In summary, the errors of judgment identified from among the plays are: lack of judgment itself in Romeo and Juliet; the fact that Lear chose between his daughters for fake love and praise, and how he wanted to hear what made him feel good; the indecisiveness of Hamlet because he is unable to decide regarding the problems he is faced with.

In addition, Antony's error is his desire to be part of the two contrasting, and at times opposing worlds; Othello, another character possesses jealousy that drives him to murder Desdemona. These errors of judgment of the characters led to their downfall. Their desires to achieve certain things caused them to commit mistakes, betrayed people unconsciously, but most of the time, it led to their own death.

Table 1 Errors of Judgment of the Characters

Characters	Error of Judgment
Romeo and Juliet	Romeo and Juliet's primary error of judgment where they were both unable or unwilling consider their actions and those actions' outcomes because they were ruled by their inner and selfish decisions therefore, acted on impulse. Their incautious acts that leads to their tragic end.
King Lear	Lear's decision of picking which daughters to take over the kingdom was his error of judgment. Lear was completely blinded by the praise of his daughters Regan and Goneril, he judges poor Cordelia's statement as an insult rather than just a true emotion from a daughter to a father. The fact Lear choses between his daughters for fake love and praise, showed how narrow minded he was, and how he just wanted to hear what made him feel good, no matter how true it was. This is what caused king Lear all of the turmoil he encountered.
Hamlet	Hamlet's error of judgment in Shakespeare's play "Hamlet" causes his tragic downfall. Hamlet's hamartia is his indecisiveness, which stems from his inability to make a decision concerning the issues he faces. His tragic flaw is 'procrastination'. Reddy (2014) said that his constant awareness and uncertainty prevent him from completing the task at hand. Claudius is ultimately killed by Hamlet, but only after he realizes he has been poisoned. His tragic flaw, procrastination, leads to his demise, as well as the downfall of the other characters he targets. However, Hamlet is not to blame for the plot's complexities. In Hamlet, fate, chance, and the supernatural all play important roles.
Antony and Cleopatra	Antony is a famous and honorable general whose reputation as a great man precedes him, but when he arrives in Egypt and falls in love with Queen Cleopatra, he faces inner conflict. The physical manifestation of the disparities between these two worlds is Antony's inner conflict: Rome represents war, honor, and duty, where military and political strength are treasured above all else. This is in stark contrast to Egypt, where court life is characterized by passion, desire, sensuality, and love. Antony's error is that he wants to be a part of both of these contrasting, and at times competing worlds: he wants to keep his power and reputation as a courageous soldier and brilliant leader inside Rome, but he also wants to enjoy a carefree life with Cleopatra.
Othello	Another Shakespearean character, Othello, has certain flaws as well. Othello erupts in a furious rage when Iago lies to him. His jealousy pushes him to murder Desdemona, and when he finds she is innocent, he kills himself.

Implication to the Teaching of Literature

Table 1 presents the errors of judgment identified in the plays involved in this study. All errors of judgment led to the tragic death of the main characters.

The play *Romeo and Juliet* is set with an acknowledgment of the fact that Romeo is to die in his own hand. It is a play on romantic love and in the unravelling of the play, love was seen as a mighty power, but destiny is mightier still.

“My only love sprung from my only fate...”

The play's error of judgment is in the characters' inability to judge. Indeed, with fate and love at first sight, the loves conflict begun and became an issue.

**“...prodigious birth of love it is me.
 That I must love a loathed...”**

Implications from the play are best shared in a literature class. Lessons learned from it are also best imparted among students. It is not only the might of the pen of the author that is to be impressed but the string of scenes which is laden with real life-like situations.

With students in a literature class who are teenagers, the error of judgment in *Romeo and Juliet* would be a star's beacon light which will guide and remind them that love is a mightier power. None escapes from this power- early or late in life.

Also, in the play *King Lear*, the error was Lear's preference to hear and listen only to what pleases him. Real life situations reveal the play's implications. The classic conflict between good and evil, and because Lear would only hear his daughters' exaggerated proclamations of love as erroneous judgment takes place.

**“If it be you that stir these daughters' hearts
 Against their father, fool me not so much
 touch me with noble anger, and let
 not women's weapons, water-drops,
 ... stain my man's cheeks!...”**

In simple terms, when in a literature class the impression of being good over others may be an example of looking at the “two sides” of a coin. The issue on women (Lear's daughters) stereotypes sibling's rivalry. Like Jocasta, mother of Oedipus who toyed with the role of authority. Lear's daughters appear to have toyed with Lear's authority as a father. Plainly, in a Filipino family parents are not to be toyed; rather they be respected. The Filipino family is laden with codes. These codes, by implication, can be made understandable in a literature class among other classes.

When Hamlet's indecisiveness went blind, reckless, and violent. He wanted revenge. As to how may this be put to lessons in a literature class goes back to the understanding that literature mirrors life - its experiences and the codes which society has constructed and dictated. Further, by implication, the error of judgment may be taught by equating it to a code coherent and understandable in ways of life. Simply, an error of judgment carries with it a value or a lesson which could be discussed in a literature class apart from appreciation of the play.

In *Antony and Cleopatra*, the error of judgment may be discussed in a literature classroom implying that none can serve two masters at the same time. That life is more of choices and priorities. As such, the young learners in a literature class may be guided as they make their decisions in school, in their family and in their community. That there is nothing less than to be rational and choose.

The play *Othello* reveals some actions that can be seen in real life view. Through his jealousy, his ego ignites his patience to lose. As Iago tricked him, that his wife is cheating with another man, his jealousy drives him to murder his beloved Desdemona.

As to the implications, the error of judgment of the protagonist may be seen as a lesson to be taught to those who values love and faith. Error of judgment involves strong connection with both mature and immature decisions. Some leads to their downfall but some walks to the path of survival. It is viewed as a lesson which could be discussed in literature class for it feeds moral values while appreciating the play.

Indeed, the work of Shakespeare is not just about stories that need to be told, but it is also about getting knowledge or lessons reflected in real life situations. Studying the tragic plays of Shakespeare is not as easy as reading educational books where the information is already stated and so easy to acquire, but it is the very complete set of codes which are to be analysed critically and comprehensively to make it more understandable and present similarly a set of codes that guides decision making, falling in love, making friends, building a name, maintaining honour, and serving the people.

Conclusion

This study dealt on the errors of judgment found in the characters, specifically the protagonist in the plays of Shakespeare, by determining the tragic flaw in terms of the events, theme, setting and characterization, and draw pedagogical implication to literature teaching. Formalistic approach and the literary device Hamartia by Aristotle underpinned this qualitative-interpretative research.

Romeo and Juliet, *King Lear*, *Othello*, *Anthony and Cleopatra*, and *Hamlet* are some tragic plays of Shakespeare. In the researchers' findings as analyzed through the lines, the plays contain tragic flaws which led to the character's tragic ends. The author established the standard structure of certain events of the play; setting has taken place by bringing the ancient times to the contemporary world where modern young readers can relate; the theme encompasses different ideas, truth, verities, and realities of life that readers can grasp from each page; the author involved tragic characters in the play so as to bring delight and relation to the tragic genre; and the writer's style involved the usage of conversational, humorous, but powerful language that need not straightjacket the readers in a forceful understanding of the play.

Furthermore, the researchers also determined how the characters committed tragic flaws in the turn of the events, theme, setting, and more importantly their characterization. With regard to the theory used by the researchers, only the protagonists of the play were selected and examined for their errors of judgment. Tragic characters only involved *Romeo*, *Juliet*, *King Lear*, *Hamlet*, *Anthony*, *Cleopatra*, and *Othello*.

Shakespearean tragedies encapsulate life's realities that readers can relate to. It does not only cater the development of reading skills, critical thinking, comprehension but also beef up their literary appreciation of life through the character portrayed in any piece of literature. The characters' deeds or actuations in the plays also reflect some tragic flaws as the cause of the tragic downfall. Some characters were able to prevent their demise, especially for the lovers in other plays who are predestined to be together, but because of their flaw, they died together.

The error of judgment which resulted to the death of the protagonist involves the death of many of neighboring characters. This is very clearly seen in the protagonist characters in selected play of Shakespeare, where their actions, or their inaction, resulted in the demise of almost all the remaining characters. Every character at some point question about the meaning of life

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